

A Linguistic Analysis of *Anam Cara*: Spiritual Wisdom from the Celtic World

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Abstract: The article presents the results of a comprehensive study of the complex cognitive-linguistic mechanisms underlying the formation and representation of spiritual-philosophical concepts in J. O'Donohue's *Anam Cara: Spiritual Wisdom from the Celtic World* (1997). Drawing on cognitive linguistics, philosophy, and cultural studies, the study illuminates how spirituality is constructed using linguistic devices in the text studied. Our findings contribute to the growing body of scientific knowledge in cognitive psychology, linguistics, and cultural studies as they elucidate the intertwined nature of cognitive processes, linguistic factors, and cultural influences in forming and interpreting spiritual and philosophical concepts. Our findings indicate that images and metaphors related to the concepts of the soul, light, and mystery are frequently employed in expressing spiritual and philosophical ideas in the novel through personifications, juxtapositions, and syntactic constructions such as parallelisms and antitheses. In conclusion, such interdisciplinary research provides a foundation for further exploration and refinement of theoretical frameworks and methodologies in these fields, contributing to research and practical application advances.

Anahtar Sözcükler:

Dilbilim
Bilişsel dilbilim
Kültürel çalışmalar
Keltler
Anam Cara

Anam Cara: Kelt Dünyasından Manevi Bilgelik'in Dilbilimsel Bir İncelemesi

Özet: Bu çalışmada, J. O'Donohue'nun *Anam Cara: Kelt Dünyasından Manevi Bilgelik* (1997) adlı eserinde manevi-felsefi kavramların oluşumu ve temsilinin altında yatan karmaşık bilişsel-dilbilimsel mekanizmaların kapsamlı bir çalışmasının sonuçlarını sunmaktadır. Bilişsel dilbilim, felsefe ve kültürel çalışmalardan yararlanan çalışma, incelenen metinde maneviyatın dilsel araçlar kullanılarak nasıl inşa edildiğini aydınlatmaktadır. Bulgularımız, bilişsel psikoloji, dilbilim ve kültürel çalışmalardaki büyüyen bilimsel bilgi birikimine katkıda bulunarak, manevi ve felsefi kavramların oluşturulması ve yorumlanmasında bilişsel süreçlerin, dilbilimsel faktörlerin ve kültürel etkilerin iç içe geçmiş doğasını açıklığa kavuşturmuştur. Bulgularımız, ruh, ışık ve gizem kavramlarıyla ilgili imgelerin ve metaforların, kişileştirmeler, yan yana koymalar ve paralellikler ve antitezler gibi sözdizimsel yapılar aracılığıyla romanda manevi ve felsefi fikirleri ifade etmede sıklıkla kullanıldığını göstermektedir. Sonuç olarak, bu tür disiplinlerarası araştırmalar, kuramsal çerçevelerin ve araştırma yöntemlerinin daha çok kullanılması için bir temel oluşturarak, benzer araştırmalar yapılmasına katkıda bulunmaktadır.

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1. Introduction

The significance of this research is underscored by the growing interest in comprehending language not only as a medium of communication but also as a repository of knowledge. Two fundamental theories are proposed from a cultural-historical perspective in cognitive semantics: the four-level theory of cognitive development and the sociocultural theory of lexical complexes and their application to the analysis of specific material (Glebkin, 2024). This interest extends to studying how language shapes our perception of the world and contributes to knowledge acquisition. The process of sense-making is complex, involving dynamic interactions between verbal and non-verbal means, different cognitive systems, and various forms of cognition (Abisheva, 2023). As information is received through multiple channels while being processed mentally and linguistically, such representations do not merely reflect objects or events. Essentially, they reflect an individual's unique perception and understanding, evident at both the conceptual and linguistic levels.

Celtic culture has always fascinated scholars (Macculloch, 2024), mainly because they influenced other European societies through technological proficiency in metallurgy, urban planning, and jewellery making (Markrof, 2021). Their technological innovations, exemplified by architectural marvels such as the city of Kelheim and the fortifications around the Heidengraben, have left an indelible mark on European history. Even in the 19th century, certain Irish writers considered themselves writers of the Celtic world (Arikan & Tekşener, 2022). Moreover, numerous contemporary European nations can trace their origins to Celtic culture, with its enduring influence on forming national identity particularly evident in the British context (Ravenna, 2023). Consequently, Celtic culture's pervasive and multifaceted influence on European civilization underscores the necessity for scientific study and understanding within modern historical and cultural studies (Rolleston, 2023).

This study analyzes the linguistic representation of spiritual and philosophical concepts in J. O'Donohue's novel *Anam Cara: Spiritual Wisdom from the Celtic World* (1997) using a comprehensive approach that integrates literary analysis, cognitive linguistics, and cultural studies. In our study, we have consulted a wide range of studies with a cognitive orientation. It is necessary to note the contribution of the following scientists to the development of individual theoretical problems of cognitive linguistics.

2. Methodology

The distributive analysis method was employed to examine the meanings associated with polysemic words resting in the text. This method was developed by Harris (2002), who asserted that the essence of this method is to study and describe languages "from within." Moreover, Kustova's (2021) work considers distributive models or distributive relations. Conceptual-representational analysis is a method within the cognitive approach to language study. A cognitive approach to the description of polysemy does not entail the inventory and classification of existing meanings but rather the identification of general regularities on the very mechanism of their formation. This enables the reconstruction of the relationship between words and their meanings, presenting them as a unified system.

Cognitive matrix modelling is a research method within cognitive matrix analysis that aims to study units of a specialized format that extends beyond the boundaries of stereotypical knowledge classifications. As mentioned above, the research aims to identify and analyze the linguistic techniques used by the author to convey spiritual and philosophical themes. This requires a comprehensive examination of the text, identifying and analyzing the recurring

motifs, symbolic images, narrative devices, and stylistic techniques used to illuminate the realms of spiritual wisdom and philosophical inspiration. Our investigation employs a comprehensive approach, integrating traditional linguistic methodologies and modern techniques, including conceptual analysis (Pathak, 2024). We regard conceptual analysis as a methodology for delineating linguistic representations of spiritual and philosophical concepts through constructing a cognitive matrix model. By integrating insights from cognitive linguistics, our study examines the intricate relationship between language structures and conceptual metaphors that underpin our comprehension of abstract concepts. Our analysis draws upon the conceptual metaphor theory developed by Guldin (2021), who identifies the cognitive mechanisms that facilitate the conceptualization and communication of abstract ideas within the narrative. In particular, the study examines the linguistic representations and cognitive mappings of spiritual experiences, existential questions, and philosophical concepts in the text.

Furthermore, our investigation incorporates cultural studies to contextualize the linguistic portrayal of spiritual and philosophical concepts within Celtic culture and spirituality (Sharifian, 2021). This entails an exploration of the historical and cultural milieu of the Celtic world depicted in the novel, coupled with an analysis of indigenous spiritual traditions, folklore, and mythological motifs that imbue the narrative with depth and meaning. By situating our analysis in a sociocultural context, our study seeks to uncover the cultural resonances and implications of linguistic expressions of spiritual wisdom and philosophical contemplation. The research adopts an interdisciplinary approach, integrating methods and theories from literary analysis, cognitive linguistics, cultural studies, and interdisciplinary perspectives to provide a nuanced understanding of how the book's spiritual and philosophical concepts are linguistically manifested. As the analysis has demonstrated, the influence of linguistic-cultural features is evident in the utilization of specialized vocabulary and imagery characteristic of Celtic culture. For example, numerous images and metaphors, such as the 'tree of life' or the 'sacred spring,' directly relate to natural phenomena and Celtic cultural traditions. This enables the reader to engage with the ideas presented more profoundly, allowing them to comprehend them within the context of their own cultural background. Moreover, specific terminology such as *Anam Cara*, which translates as "soul mate" in Gaelic, reflects the Celtic concept of spiritual connection among people. Using the terminology of spiritual practices and rituals, such as "sacred rite of contemplation" or "path of wisdom," not only serves to convey the distinctive nature of Celtic culture but also enhances the comprehension of the spiritual concepts presented in the narrative.

It is widely acknowledged that language serves a distinctive function: interpreting the world and our knowledge of it (Lappin, 2021). This function is unique to language and cannot be replicated by any other means. This research is focused on the anthropocentric nature of language and cognition. We contend that the content of linguistic meaning is directly related to the author's conceptual system and constitutes an integral part of the human cognitive system. Furthermore, it is acknowledged that the interpretive function of language is inextricably linked to how humans perceive the world around them. Language is understood to influence, mediate, and enable all cognitive processes. As Lappin (2021) posits, it is only possible to describe the world if there are adequate means of description and appropriate names. Both theories define linguistic interpretation as a cognitive activity expressed in language. This conceptualization suggests that the acquisition of knowledge is a collective process. In a more restricted sense, it is an individual linguistic and cognitive process that conveys the subjective perception of the object of interpretation. In other words, it is a projection of the world or knowledge about the world that is immersed in an individual's

collective or individual linguistic consciousness. By the theoretical framework proposed by Aramida *et al.* (2023), we posit that the cognitive model synthesizes three key concepts: frame elements, cognitive spaces, and cluster correspondences.

Frame elements represent fundamental cognitive structures that describe knowledge about specific concepts or situations. To illustrate, the frame “family” may comprise elements such as “parents,” “children,” and “siblings,” among others. Cognitive spaces, expressed as a concept map, represent the relationships between different concepts or ideas organized in a particular structure or sequence. A concept map of friendship might include relationships between love, friendship, and mutual understanding. Furthermore, cluster correspondences consider the individual characteristics and experiences of the subject that influence the perception and interpretation of cognitive elements. This cognitive model synthesizes various theories and concepts in cognitive linguistics (Deckert *et al.*, 2023). It serves as a tool for analyzing the structure of knowledge and representations of the world. The model views thinking as an internal process and an active, interacting system that includes internal and external elements. Consequently, using the cognitive matrix model in the analysis enables considering internal and external factors that influence the meanings of various language uses.

The model elucidates how these concepts are understood and interpreted using illustrative linguistic examples, such as imagery, metaphors, symbols, and cultural contexts (Kozhbayeva, 2023). By examining these cognitive structures, the model facilitates a deeper understanding of how spiritual ideas influence human perception and comprehension of the world. The cognitive matrix model is based on the fundamental principles of cognitive linguistics and outlines three key elements of cognitive structures: frameworks, cognitive spaces, and cluster correspondences. Each element plays a distinctive role in the organization of our conceptual understanding of diverse phenomena and situations. This model analyzes systems of spiritual and philosophical concepts, as exemplified in the text analyzed. Integrating linguistic, cultural, and conceptual components within the cognitive matrix model enables a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of how these concepts shape our perceptual paradigms and influence our behavioral predispositions.

3. Findings

The interpretation of concepts such as geometric figures, including the line, spiral, and circle, about the characteristics of the Celtic mind generates new meanings of a generalizing nature. These meanings demonstrate that the Celtic consciousness historically eschewed the pursuit of absolute certainty in its reflections on being. The Celtic consciousness embodies spiritual meanings with multifaceted, hidden, symbolic significance. The cognitive mechanisms responsible for generating these secondary meanings are conceptual metaphor and concretization (Deckert *et al.*, (2023). These are manifested through linguistic metaphors, including personification, concretizing epithets, and paraphrases. For instance, the Celtic mind was never inclined towards pursuing single-line certainty; it eschewed any mode of perception or existence, seeking satisfaction by attaining absolute truth. In contrast, it profoundly respected the enigmatic nature of the circle and the spiral. These are the interpretations of the world and knowledge about the world in language, which may be termed primary and secondary linguistic interpretations of the world.

Primary interpretation is characterized by individuals’ active, purposeful participation in structuring the world and schematizing their interaction experiences (Appendix 1). This process involves the identification of units of knowledge (concepts) through language and

their subsequent combination into categories with shared language designations. For example, a higher occurrence of terms such as “soul” and “spirituality” may indicate a thematic emphasis on human introspection, spiritual quests, and mystical dimensions. The semantic domain surrounding the concept of “soul” may include notions such as “essence,” “inner sanctum,” “individuality,” and “spirituality,” indicating profound inner landscapes of humanity. Examining associative networks and metaphoric constructs associated with each concept facilitates the comprehension of the author’s conceptual portrayal and the imagery employed to convey them. For instance, metaphorically, using a “circle” may convey the concept of boundlessness. The text refers to the soul as the inner sanctum of humans, shrouded in mystery and unfathomability. The text portrays the soul as an enigmatic realm, emphasizing its profound and mystical essence. The text further dwells upon the spiritual aspects of existence, highlighting their intricacies and profundity, the interconnection between secrecy and sanctity, denoting the spiritual essence of secrecy and its significance in human experience.

Furthermore, the text employs a variety of images and metaphors associated with love to illustrate its harmony, grandeur, and transformative potential. For instance, the text employs light imagery to underscore the harmony and splendor of nature, illuminating each stone with the most harmonious angle of light. Friendship is a singular and irreplaceable entity concerning each bond’s individuality and intrinsic value. Each stone has its own distinctive appearance (Appendix 2). This expression correlates with the uniqueness of every friendship. The concept of death is depicted as an integral facet of existence, intertwined with memory, history, and enigmas. For example, the author posits that the landscape evokes recollection and history. This illustrates the enduring nature of memory and the intertwining of nature with recollection. Destiny is a preordained and eternal phenomenon interwoven with the tapestry of life. To illustrate this, the author draws attention to the significance of stones as a symbol of eternity, thereby emphasizing the impact of time and destiny upon the living milieu. Categorization, in its most general sense, can be defined as organizing and structuring knowledge acquired throughout an individual’s lifespan. This process allows individuals to make sense of the world by dividing it into distinct parts, creating a more ordered and manageable framework for the mind to comprehend (Zalabardo, 2023).

A comprehensive analysis of the dominant concepts in the text elucidates the spiritual, social, and philosophical aspects of Celtic civilization. It comprehensively explains the Celtic people's intricate social dynamics and historical evolution. Considering these, it can be reasonably proposed that:

1. The human mind creates a distinct world within the boundaries of consciousness through multiple forms of representation, including linguistic interpretation. These representations are the foundation for our perception and comprehension of the world. Hence, each individual encapsulates distinct concepts and perceptions that frame their understanding.
2. The organization of linguistic elements, or framing, plays a pivotal role in influencing interpretation and the construction of subjective meaning, particularly within the context of spirituality. Language and linguistic structures enable individuals to express their spiritual ideas and concepts and to perceive their meaning and significance.
3. Expressive techniques, such as diverse linguistic expression methods, provide a framework for formalizing, communicating, and profoundly reflecting on spiritual ideas and concepts. These means contribute to a more comprehensive understanding

and interpretation of spiritual concepts within the context of linguistic design, thereby enriching the perception and exchange of spiritual ideas within society.

Utilizing the cognitive matrix model as an integrative analytical paradigm facilitated a more profound examination of the linguistic representation of spiritual-philosophical concepts in terms of cognitive processes and perceptual mechanisms. This model postulates that cognitive processes are pivotal in the genesis and interpretation of spiritual concepts, conceived as intricate networks of interconnected ideas and representations. By meticulously examining various textual elements, including linguistic structures, metaphors, symbols, and sociocultural contexts, the model facilitates a nuanced examination of the intertwined nature of spiritual concepts and their impact on human cognition and worldviews. Furthermore, it provides a foundation for further research in cognitive linguistics, philosophy, and cultural studies (He, 2022).

4. Conclusion

The findings of the study elucidate the intricate dynamics underlying the construction and interpretation of subjective meanings within the domain of spirituality. Images and metaphors related to the concepts of the soul, light, and mystery are frequently employed in expressing spiritual and philosophical ideas. Such images facilitate the communication of complex ideas and evoke a sense of deep inner comprehension. The text employs many metonymic and metaphorical devices to convey abstract concepts through concrete images and phenomena, thereby rendering them more accessible and comprehensible to the reader. As the analysis has demonstrated, the most prevalent technique employed in representing spiritual and philosophical ideas is the personification of an object or concept. This involves ascribing human characteristics to an inanimate object or concept, creating a sense of vitality and activity. In this context, it is evident that linguistic representation is employed in describing spiritual and philosophical concepts that contain emotional content and convey feelings such as delight, awe, and inner harmony. The concept of opposition is also evident in images. They emphasize the duality and interrelationship of opposites. One illustrative example is the juxtaposition of "wild but calm complexity" and "mystery and holiness as sisters." Syntactic constructions of a complex nature, such as parallelism, antithesis, and introductory constructions, were employed to emphasize the depth and complexity of spiritual ideas.

Based on these results, we propose a matrix model postulating a linguistic representation of the cognitive mechanisms underlying the perception and learning of spiritual concepts. The cognitive matrix model, situated within cognitive linguistics and cognitive science domains, provides a robust foundation for comprehending the intricate nuances of spiritual and philosophical concepts. It meticulously delineates the impact of language, culture, and conceptual frameworks on information assimilation and comprehension processes. By furnishing researchers and analysts with analytical instruments, the model facilitates the investigation of the intricate intricacies inherent in spirituality, philosophy, and culture, thereby elucidating various aspects of these phenomena.

In other words, the strategic use of language tools such as metaphors, symbols, and rhetorical strategies is designed to elicit subtle cognitive responses and associations in readers deeply rooted in their individual ideas about spirituality and philosophical considerations. Furthermore, the novel's meticulously crafted temporal and spatial landscapes create a tangible atmosphere and context for the narrative, fostering a deeper understanding and engagement with the spiritual and philosophical themes permeating the text.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 28/07/2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. *Types of Linguistic Interpretation*

Type	Implementation	Functions
Primary (objective) linguistic interpretation of the world	The collective understanding of the world within a society is manifested through the collective perception of individuals.	The interpretation and evaluation of objects is contingent upon the specific domains within which they are situated.
	Units of knowledge (concepts) are grouped into categories with a common linguistic name.	Events are interpreted through the establishment of multiple connections among different domains. Various techniques are employed to organize the conceptual-thematic domain, including linguistic methods.
<p>“For millions of years, an ancient conversation has continued between the chorus of the ocean and the silence of the stone.” This sentence clearly describes the ongoing interaction between natural elements (ocean and stone) over an extended period. The text employs a propositional structure and metaphorical models to convey the enduring relationship between these elements and their impact on the Irish landscape. “The mystery of this landscape is further intensified by the presence of the ocean.” The presence of the ocean intensifies the area's mystery, which is conveyed directly through the description of the landscape and its mystery. The ocean is identified as a significant factor in enhancing this mystery, and cognitive mechanisms such as profiling and metaphorical models are employed to convey the relationship between the landscape and the ocean.</p>		
Secondary (subjective) interpretation of world knowledge through language)	<p>The interpretation of collective knowledge and collective cognitive schemata within the individual conceptual system of a given person.</p> <p>Individuals organize their perceptions of the world and structure their experiences by schematizing their interactions.</p>	Interpreting linguistic elements and categories enables the organization and expression of subjective perceptions and cognitive schemes within individual conceptual frameworks.
<p>“The Celtic mind was never drawn to the single line; it avoided ways of seeing and being which seek satisfaction in certainty.” The secondary linguistic interpretation is evident as it characterizes the Celtic mind metaphorically, attributing cognitive tendencies and philosophical inclinations to it. This interpretation goes beyond the text's literal meaning, delving into abstract concepts related to the Celtic consciousness and its approach to knowledge and certainty. “Here, it feels as if a wild, surrealistic God laid down the whole landscape.” This exemplifies the secondary linguistic interpretation, metaphorically attributes creative agency to God, and characterizes the landscape as surrealistic. This invokes abstract concepts and deeper symbolic meanings associated with the landscape, which extend beyond its immediate physical attributes.</p>		

Appendix 2. *The linguistic representation of spiritual and philosophical concepts in J. O'Donohue's novel Anam Cara: Spiritual Wisdom from the Celtic World*

Concept	Text Fragment	Linguistic Mechanism	Interpretation
Soul	“I was born in a limestone valley.”	The sentence is straightforward and employs a specific geological descriptor. It comprises a lexical nomination, a profiling, and a metaphorical epithet, namely "limestone valley."	A valley of limestone rock. The limited sky creates a sense of solitude. The soul of the landscape is expressed in the uniqueness of each stone.
	“The soul of nature is expressed as an ongoing chorus of praise.”	Linguistic metaphor, inversion, figurative meaning, transformation (frame → frame), passive construction with logical inversion.	The soul of nature is a constant choir of praise.
	“The soul of the landscape is filled with memory.”	The sentence lacks complex grammatical structures and comprises a subject, verb, and object. It employs a subject-verb-object structure and inversion. The	The horizon line frames the living space.

		language employed in the sentence is metaphorical, with the verb "filled" conveying the idea of memory.	
	"The curvature and diversity of the landscape underline its depth of meaning."	Personification: the curvature and diversity of the landscape serve to illustrate the depth of meaning inherent in the landscape itself.	The landscape's curvature and diversity illustrate the depth of meaning inherent in the landscape itself.
	"The presence of the ocean further intensifies the mystery of this landscape."	The sentence is complex in structure due to the subject-verb-object format. The text employs lexical nomination and linguistic metaphor, as evidenced by the phrases "the mystery of this landscape" and "the presence of the ocean."	The presence of the ocean further compounds the enigmatic quality of this landscape.
	"An ancient conversation has continued between the ocean's chorus and the stone's silence."	The sentence is compound, with subject, verb, and object structure. The metaphors used in the sentence are 'conversation', 'the chorus of the ocean' and 'the silence of the stone.'	Ancient conversation... chorus of the ocean and the silence of the stone
Friendship	"No two stone shapes in this landscape are the same."	The sentence is devoid of any complex grammatical structures and is expressed straightforwardly. It employs a negative form conveyed through the metaphor "stone shapes."	Each stone has its own face.
	"Each stone has a different face."	Simple declarative sentence with subject-verb-object structure; Metaphor - "stone," "different face."	Each stone is unique.
Love	"The angle of the light brings out the shy presence of each stone."	The sentence is complex due to its combination of independent and dependent clauses and contains metaphors that enhance the imagery and meaning conveyed.	The light highlights each stone.
	"The landscape feels as if a wild, surrealistic God laid it down."	The sentence is complex, with a subject-verb-object structure. It employs a metaphor, describing the landscape as a wild, surrealistic God who laid it down.	The landscape evokes the impression of having been created by a divine force that is both wild and surrealistic.
Death	"These stones, ever patient, ever still, continue to praise the silence of time."	Complex sentence with compound subject and predicate; Metaphor - "stones," "patient, still," "praise the silence of time."	Curvature...frustrates the eye
	"The Irish landscape, it holds memory, holds ..."	Simple declarative sentence with a parenthetical; Personification - "landscape holds memory."	Stern color, delicate line
	"There is a curvature in the landscape, a color and shape that constantly frustrates the eye anxious..."	Compound sentence with subject-verb-object structure; Metaphor - "curvature in the landscape," "color and shape."	Landscape changes...call the imagination.
	"This landscape has a wild, yet serene complexity."	Simple declarative sentence; metaphor - "landscape", "wild yet serene complexity."	Landscape has... complexity.
Spirituality	"In a sense, this reflects the nature of Celtic consciousness."	The sentence lacks a specific syntactic structure beyond the prepositional phrase and the independent clause, which serves to provide context or qualification for the main statement.	This landscape reflects... Celtic Consciousness
	"The Celtic mind was never drawn to the single line; it avoided ways of seeing and being which seek satisfaction..."	A compound sentence is constituted by two independent clauses connected by a semicolon. Each clause contributes to the sentence's overall meaning, describing different aspects of the Celtic mind's characteristics and tendencies.	Celtic mind... avoided ways
	"The Celtic mind had a wonderful respect for the mystery of the circle and the spiral."	The sentence is straightforward and employs a metaphorical comparison, namely the concept of the "Celtic mind" and the "mystery of the circle and the spiral." Simple declarative sentence,	Mystery of the circle and the spiral

	metaphor - "Celtic mind," "mystery of the circle and the spiral."	
"...one of the oldest and most powerful symbols."	The sentence is unambiguous and declarative, and it employs emotional epithets, such as "oldest" and "most powerful."	One of the oldest... symbols
"The world is a circle; the sun and moon are too."	The sentence is devoid of any complex syntax and employs a language metaphor, namely the comparison of the world to a circle.	The world is a circle; the sun and moon are too
"Even time itself has a circular nature; the day and the year build to a circle."	The sentence is straightforward and declarative, emphatically asserting the circular nature of time. The metaphor "day and the year build to a circle» illustrates this concept, comparing the passage of time to the cyclical nature of the day and the year.	Even time itself has... a circle.
"At its most intimate level, so is the life of each individual."	The sentence lacks complex syntactic structures. In a simple declarative statement, the pronoun "its" is pronominalized, indicating the sentence is represented at the most intimate level.	Life=circle
"The circle never gives itself completely to the eye or to the mind, but offers a trusting hospitality to that which is complex and mysterious; it embraces depth and height together."	The sentence is complex and parallel and features personification, as evidenced by the phrase, "The circle never gives itself completely to the eye or to the mind."	Circle never gives itself
"Patience with this reserve is one of the profound recognitions of the Celtic mind."	The sentence is complex. The subject is Patience, the predicate - "is," and the complement is "one of the profound recognitions of the Celtic mind."	Circle never reduces the mystery
"The world of the soul is secret."	A sentence of a relatively simple structure: The subject is the world of the soul, the predicate is "is," and the complement is "secret." This is a metaphorical periphrasis.	Patience with this reserve
"The secret and the sacred are sisters."	A sentence of a relatively simple structure: The subject of the sentence is "The secret and the sacred." The predicate is "are," and the complement is "sisters." The sentence is personified.	World of the soul is secret